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ASSESSMENT OF THE CURRENT STATUS OF USING ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT TOOLS IN ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT AT SEAPORTS IN VIETNAM

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Annotation: Using environmental impact assessment tools to forecast, evaluate and propose solutions to minimize the impact of seaports on the environment is very necessary. However, the use of this tool in environmental management at seaports in Vietnam still has many limitations. This article addresses some limitations and proposes solutions to improve the effectiveness of using this tool in environmental management at Vietnamese seaports.

Keywords: seaports, environmental impact assessment, environmental management

ОЦЕНКА ТЕКУЩЕГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ОЦЕНКИ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ НА ОКРУЖАЮЩУЮ СРЕДУ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДОЙ В МОРСКИХ ПОРТАХ ВО ВЬЕТНАМЕ

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Аннотация: Использование инструментов оценки воздействия на окружающую среду для прогнозирования, оценки и предложения решений по минимизации воздействия морских портов на окружающую среду крайне необходимо. Однако использование этого инструмента в управлении окружающей средой в морских портах Вьетнама по-прежнему имеет много ограничений. В этой статье

рассматриваются некоторые ограничения и предлагаются решения для повышения эффективности использования этого инструмента в управлении окружающей средой в морских портах Вьетнама.

Ключевые слова: морские порты, оценка воздействия на окружающую среду, управление окружающей средой

1. The role of environmental impact assessment in environmental management of seaports

Seaport development always comes with unwanted environmental impacts during the construction and operation stages of ports. The construction phase always causes impacts on the environment of air, water, soil, sediment, and ecosystems due to the transportation of raw materials, the operation of construction machinery and equipment, and human activities. Table 1 presents the main impacts of the seaport construction phase on the environment.

Table 1 – Summary of main sources of impacts during the construction phase

Major sources of environmental impact	Major pollutants	Environmental components affected
Waste related		
Site clearance and preparation activities Port yard surface reinforcement activities Installation of machinery and equipment Material transportation activities Exhaust fumes from engines of construction machinery and trucks Surface coating process	TSP, CO, CO ₂ , NO _x , SO _x , VOC, CH ₄ , HC...	Air environment Soil environment
Port construction Dredging of shipping channels and water areas in front of the wharf Land filling Construction and installation of wharves Transport of machinery and materials Ship operations Operation of machinery and equipment	Solid waste Domestic waste, domestic wastewater Wastewater from maintenance, repair and discharge Oil	Water environment

Major sources of environmental impact	Major pollutants	Environmental components affected
Oil spills Domestic activities		
Clearing and preparing the site Reinforcing the port yard surface Construction of the port yard and office building, warehouse Construction of access roads... Activities of those participating in the construction of the project	Construction waste Hazardous waste Domestic waste	Soil environment
Site clearance and preparation Port construction Wharf leveling Equipment operation Vessel operations Oil spills	Domestic waste Wastewater from ships Sand fill Oil	Ecosystems
No waste involved		
Construction activities	Noise and vibration	
Dredging activities		Has the ability to change the flow regime causing erosion
Transport of raw materials		Water and road transport

When the port is in operation, the main sources of environmental impacts are:

- ship operations;
- goods spilled during loading and unloading;
- operations of loading and unloading vehicles and equipment, and cargo transportation;
- solid waste from cargo handling areas, vehicle repair and maintenance workshops;
- domestic waste of port workers and crew members of ships calling at the port;
- accidents related to ships entering and leaving the port;
- incidents during fuel storage and supply.

Table 2 – Summary of sources of impacts during port operations

No	Source of impact	Potential waste generation	Affected objects
	Waste related		
1	Dredging and maintaining the water area in front of the wharf	Bottom mud, oil and grease from dredging equipment	Water Environment Aquatic Ecosystem
2	Operation of means of circulation	Dust, exhaust, noise	Air Environment Worker
3	Receiving and shipping activities in the port area	Dust, exhaust gas, noise, solid waste	Air Environment Worker
4	Port cleaning activities	Industrial wastewater, solid waste	Water environment
5	Other activities in the port	Oil contaminated wastewater, solid waste	Water Environment Aquatic Ecosystems
6	Activities of officers and employees in the port	Waste and domestic wastewater	Water Environment Soil Environment Air Environment
7	Vessel collision, fuel storage and supply incidents	Oil Spill	Water Environment Aquatic Ecosystem
	No waste involved		
1	Operation of means of transport		Regional water and road transport
2	Dredging and maintaining the water area in front of the wharf		Potential to alter flow regime causing erosion Waterway

The main role of environmental impact assessment in port development includes:

- systematically analyzing, forecasting, and evaluating the impacts on the natural and social environment of a seaport construction project [2];

- presenting a synchronous solution on management and technology to prevent and minimize negative impacts on the natural and social environment;

– developing an environmental monitoring and management program to determine the accuracy of assessments as well as the effectiveness of pollution mitigation solutions and impacts occurring in practice.

2. Some limitations in environmental impact assessment of seaports in Vietnam

2.1. Issues related to project profile research

Project profile research plays a very important role in assessing the environmental impact of port works, shipping channels and inland waterways. However, currently, some environmental impact assessment reports have been prepared but the environmental impact assessment team has not carefully studied the project content. This is reflected in the summary of the main contents of the project, which has differences in project information compared to the investment project (feasibility study report). Incorrect information often includes: project scale, project implementation location, construction measures, project implementation time.

The role of environmental impact assessment is to assess, forecast and propose measures to minimize impacts. Failure to carefully study the content of the project dossier can lead to consequences such as:

- the environmental impact assessment report (EIA report) is not close to the project content;
- the scale of impact in terms of space and time of the project has not been properly assessed;
- the proposed impact mitigation measures are theoretical, too general, not linked to the project content and are difficult to implement or very expensive to implement.

2.2. Issues related to surveys

One of the common problems when conducting environmental impact assessments for waterway transport projects is:

- projects are often implemented in locations that are difficult to move;
- difficulty in determining the location and boundaries of the project;
- lack of data on the current state of natural conditions and the environment in the project implementation area.

The above difficulties lead to data on the current state of natural conditions, environment and socio-economy presented in the environmental impact assessment report being sketchy, not sufficient to assess the impact.

2.3. Issues related to community consultation

Almost all environmental impact assessment processes used in the world have a step of community consultation. In developed countries, this work is carried out very effectively. However, in some countries, mainly developing countries, community consultation still faces many difficulties due to limited funding, poor organization methods, low participation awareness of the people, etc. However, this is a very important step that needs to be done well in the environmental impact assessment process [1-5].

The basic purpose of consulting the community in the environmental impact assessment process is to enhance the ability to use input information and feelings from government agencies, citizens and interested communities to improve the quality of environmental decision-making. The interested groups here can include representatives of many industries and social classes.

During the process of public consultation for many environmental impact assessment reports, some benefits and disadvantages of this work have been drawn. The benefits of public consultation are only achieved when those affected are allowed to present their views. The following three main benefits can be listed:

- creating a mechanism for information exchange [3-6];
- can provide a source of information on local values;
- increasing the reliability of planning and assessment processes.

In addition, public consultation, the responsibility of project owners and environmental impact assessment teams is enhanced. It is considered an agent for checking, commenting, and evaluating the environmental impact assessment process when this process is made public.

However, community consultation also has some disadvantages, costs including the possibility of confusion, confusion, the possibility of errors in information from the community due to limited qualifications. In addition, it can slow down the process of implementing environmental impact assessment and projects, increasing project costs. However, if well organized, it will promote the strengths and limit the weaknesses of community consultation.

Community consultation is related to all steps of environmental impact assessment, from detecting impact issues, planning management and detecting issues and impacts, minimizing impacts, comparing alternative options for decision-making related to the proposed activity, to studying the drafted documents.

Right from the problem detection stage, on the one hand, it is necessary to provide information to the community about the project as well as identify groups of people who are likely to benefit, groups of people who are disadvantaged when implementing the project. In addition, provide the community with all the issues that will be considered in the environmental impact assessment. The reverse information is often existing databases to help reduce the time and cost of surveying. In addition, citizens also help identify areas of concern to the community that need to be clarified in the environmental impact assessment report.

In the forecasting and impact assessment steps, the community can support the evaluation of alternatives to ensure that projects with good prospects are not overlooked. In cases where legal standards are not in effect, comments from the community can be used to establish their own standards.

In other steps, community participation also brings practical benefits to the environmental impact assessment process. The problem is how to ensure enthusiastic contributions from the community. To do this, it is not possible to consult everywhere, but to have a good plan that satisfies the following factors:

- identifying the objectives of participation in the appropriate stages of the environmental impact assessment process;
- anticipating the communities that can be attracted to the stages of the environmental impact assessment;
- choosing the most appropriate participation method to approach the subjects and communicate with the community;
- planning the implementation of the community participation program.

In practice, the level of community participation can also be divided into 3 levels:

- not participating or not participating;
- participating in specific consultation;
- participating at the level of integration, delegation, control.

However, community participation usually stops at the second level, and the highest level rarely occurs, except in the case of a referendum.

The identification of communities is also raised in the environmental impact assessment process. The community here can be a person or a group of people with the same interests and rights. In the EIA process, information on impacts needs to be presented according to the objects of the affected communities. That is, we must identify specific communities related to the project. In reality, the community here is not a homogeneous entity but is very dispersed, and can be grouped into groups with common purposes, ideas or interests. A person can belong to several community groups, which can be professional groups, social groups or even political groups.

Although there are very specific regulations in legal documents on collecting community opinions on investment projects, including seaport construction investment projects. However, the process of collecting public opinions is often procedural, and those directly affected by the project, such as fishermen and marine aquaculture, are not consulted. On the other hand, the environmental impact assessment report is sometimes not made public so that interested communities can access it.

2.4. Issues related to report writing

All research and assessment results on environmental impacts must be selected and presented in the environmental impact assessment report. Therefore, the report drafting stage plays an important role.

The purpose of preparing an EIA report is to provide information to:

1. Support the project in planning, designing and implementing the project in the direction of eliminating or minimizing harmful impacts on the economic, social, physical and biological environments, maximizing all benefits that the project can bring.

2. Help the government or local authorities decide to approve (or not approve) the project along with the deadline and conditions that need to be applied.

3. Help the community better understand the project, its impacts on the environment and human life.

The two main requirements of the EIA report have been summarized as follows:

1. The EIA report must be clear and easy to understand. Environmental science is very complex, the scientific content considered in the EIA is very rich. However, the final users of the EIA results are sometimes not scientists but managers. Therefore, the EIA report must be clear, easy to understand, using common language and terminology. The presentation must be specific, practical, and convincing to help decision makers see the problem clearly and objectively, thereby making correct and timely decisions.

2. EIA reports must be legally rigorous. EIA reports are not only a scientific basis but also a legal basis, helping to decide on important issues of economic and social development; related to the lives and material and spiritual interests of people in a country or a locality.

In addition, EIA reports are also documents providing information for environmental management as well as the EIA process of subsequent projects.

Therefore, drafting reports must be considered one of the most important stages in the EIA process, requiring the concentration of intelligence of many experts in different fields.

The stage of drafting EIA reports is very important, because EIA reports are the summary results of an environmental impact assessment process. However, there are currently many problems surrounding the quality of EIA reports.

1. Regarding the structure of the report

Although the structure of the report has been specified in Form No. 4, Appendix II of Circular No. 02/2022/TT-BTNMT, many reports are presented without this structure.

2. Regarding the information used in the report

A current situation is that much information and data used in EIA reports do not have an original source.

3. Regarding impact assessment and forecasting

– many assessments are qualitative, and the source of emissions causing impacts has not been quantified;

The environmental impact assessment itself is to analyze, forecast and assess the environmental impacts of activities that have not yet occurred. Therefore, it is difficult to quantify the entire assessment results.

– assessments mainly focus on assessing environmental pollution, not paying much attention to assessing how environmental change will impact the ecosystem.

4. Regarding proposed mitigation measures

From the analysis of the environmental impacts of the project, it is shown that when the project is in operation, it will cause many harmful as well as beneficial impacts. In this section, we will discuss the identification of methods to minimize harmful impacts and manage environmental impacts.

The purpose of this work is:

1. To find the best implementation methods to eliminate or minimize harmful impacts and maximize the use of beneficial impacts [1].

2. To ensure that the community or individuals do not have to bear costs that exceed the benefits they receive.

To achieve this goal, the mitigation options must be implemented at the right time and in the right way as stated in the EIA report.

Before proceeding to the step of finding measures to minimize and manage impacts, it is necessary to collect the following information:

– research results on the issue of minimizing and managing impacts;

– contact organizations, agencies, and individuals who can provide information related to the issues of concern;

– other sources of information.

This will be the basis for considering and finding the most effective measures to minimize and manage impacts.

First, we consider the responsibility of the project owner in implementing mitigation measures and the long-term benefits that can be brought to the project owner when implementing these measures.

In reality, adverse impacts often exceed the scope of the project, meaning that they affect the surrounding area. Such externalities require costs to overcome, but these costs are not taken into account in the economic analysis of the project and must be paid by the social community. Therefore, to ensure sustainable development, the project owner must be responsible for calculating additional external costs throughout the project's life. This is the basis for the state and agencies to require project owners to implement mitigation measures to avoid or minimize impacts through

changing the design plan, making impact management plans, and keeping them acceptable.

While many project owners complain that accumulating external costs increases the cost of the project, many have realized that a good design and a good management plan will help save large amounts. In many cases, implementing mitigation can cause large costs in the short term but if calculated over a long period, it is cheaper.

To have effective mitigation measures, it is clear that it is necessary to grasp the nature, scale of impacts and related issues. First of all, it is necessary to know the nature of the problem, consider the relationship with public health, ecosystems, resource depletion and the environment. If it is pollution, it is necessary to pay attention to the source of pollution, whether it is a point source, a road or a surface source, and also know the potential harm of the waste. Next, we must consider whether the problem is urgent, meaning the impact is immediate or latent, and then decide whether to minimize it or wait for more information. Next, we need to understand the community's awareness of these issues, and if they are affected, can the people prevent or minimize the impact? Another issue is who will benefit, who will bear the costs, and whether it is possible to reduce harmful impacts through subsidies to compensate for the damage.

From the above understanding, it will help decide on measures to implement harmful impact mitigation. Usually, these measures must be considered and decided by the project owner, specifically the designers and the EIA team. Based on the nature of the impact and the adjustments in the design process, we can choose some of the following directions to handle and manage the issues:

- propose new methods to meet the needs;
- change the planning and design;
- strengthen management and control activities;
- change the location of the project, accommodation or residence.

However, there are many different approaches to implementing mitigation and impact management measures. Sometimes people in the EIA team are too focused on finding modern measures to solve big problems and forget about the common but also very effective measures.

Thus, almost all stages, construction, operation and project management processes must implement many mitigation measures. Normally in developed countries, some measures have been regulated, such

as large construction works must have a shielding layer, some items must be done at night. However, some developing countries do not have such regulations, so the EIA report must visualize all impacts and mitigation measures.

One point to note is that impact mitigation and waste treatment can cause other impacts. For example, to treat waste, if burned, it will cause air pollution, if buried, it will cause water pollution, and environmental sanitation will not be guaranteed. Therefore, it is necessary to balance mitigation measures, find and apply the most effective and practical mitigation system. This is a very complicated and controversial task, and is also one of the reasons why community consultation is needed throughout the EIA process. Many mitigation measures are included in the report.

2.5. Issues related to coordination of stakeholders

It can be said that in the current environmental impact assessment work, there are still many shortcomings in the coordination between the project owner and the consulting unit. According to the provisions of the Law on Environmental Protection No. 72/2020/QH14, the project owner must be responsible for the quality of the environmental impact assessment report to the state management agencies on the environment, the consulting unit (in case the project owner hires it) is responsible to the project owner for the data and results stated in the environmental impact assessment report. However, currently, some project owners consider the preparation of the report and the quality of the report to be the responsibility of the consulting unit, without carefully reviewing the content of the report. This leads to the following consequences:

1. The EIA report does not fully show, or does not correctly show, the content of the project in terms of the location, scale of the project, construction measures, and project implementation progress.

2. Commitments on impact mitigation measures, environmental management and monitoring programs are not fully implemented because the project owner does not fully understand the commitments in the EIA report or the proposed mitigation measures are difficult to implement, and the costs are too high to be feasible.

2.6. The issue of using EIA results

First of all, EIA results must be sent to the group of competent leaders as a document to help make decisions on whether to implement the project or not. In fact, this document is only one of the documents needed

to make decisions, besides it, there are also economic and technical arguments of the project and other documents. To perform the function of providing documents for decision making, the submitted document must be based on a scientific analysis of the benefits and losses to resources and the environment that the project brings. Many times, a thick report but the necessary information is lacking, so it is still not very helpful. This is very likely to happen in developing countries where there may be a lack of basic information data.

If we know how to use the above information well, it can help agencies and communities in their work. However, in reality, many times the results of EIA have not been fully exploited, so the effectiveness of this work is limited.

In fact, in Vietnam today, many project owners only consider the preparation of EIA reports as a procedure to meet the requirements of the law on environmental protection. Many project owners do not use the results of EIA reports throughout the project implementation process, so the commitments and impact mitigation measures are not fully used when implementing the project.

2.7. Post-project control and audit are also rarely performed

Environmental impact audit after project implementation is also a task required by EIA. The two main purposes of this work are:

- based on measurement and control data to correct and improve the ability to predict impacts;
- to be the basis to help improve project results.

Thus, post-project environmental control and audit work is also to serve the project, but it is often not given attention. Some of the causes leading to this situation are similar to the causes leading to the inability to implement measures to reduce harmful impacts. But another common cause in developing countries is that project owners do not pay much attention to environmental issues in general and environmental audit work in particular. Maybe they do not fully understand the effects of this work or are too busy with production and business activities to forget this function.

2.8. Risk and social impact assessment are sometimes overlooked

These are two issues that are considered the most comprehensive assessment part in EIA. However, they are sometimes ignored and not considered, especially when the risk or social impact is large.

One of the reasons is that the regulations and laws related to EIA often only emphasize physical and biological impacts.

The second reason is that the standard characteristics for assessing social impacts or risks are not clear and there are no specific instructions on assessing these two types of impacts.

Another reason is that the sense of responsibility of the project owner is not high and the qualifications of the assessors are limited.

3. Solutions to improve the effectiveness of environmental impact assessment tools in seaport environmental management

To improve the quality of environmental impact assessment reports, the following urgent measures need to be taken:

1. It is necessary to promote the implementation of the provisions of the Law on Environmental Protection and legal documents related to environmental impact assessment. In particular, environmental impact assessment must be considered an important tool to contribute to the prevention of pollution and environmental degradation.

2. One of the bases for environmental impact assessment is to compare the assessment results with environmental standards. To ensure the assessment is highly effective, it is necessary to develop a system of environmental standards suitable for each area based on the pollution coefficient and the environmental load coefficient in a narrow range.

3. The appraisal of EIA reports must be closely linked to the actual survey at the project implementation site, ensuring that the appraisal results are scientifically and practically based to be sent to the agency approving the EIA report.

4. Promote inspection and confirmation activities after the appraisal of EIA reports. Resolutely handle projects according to the provisions of law that the project owner intentionally fails to implement.

4. Conclusion

Environmental impact assessment is an environmental management tool that is being used very effectively in environmental protection when developing investment projects. Research to find out the limitations and propose solutions to improve the effectiveness of this tool in seaport

environmental management plays a very important role in identifying and minimizing negative impacts on the environment.

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